

Leadership Behavior on Organizational Performance in Indonesian Government

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ABSTRACT: This research generally aims to determine the influence of leadership behaviour on organizational performance through the values of religiosity and organizational commitment in the Jambi provincial government. Based on an understanding of these objectives, the researcher used the Grand Theory a human resource management which is related to the Middle Range Theory is organizational behaviour which is the scientific parent of the research and the Applied Theory used in this research is the Leadership Style Theory: Leadership behaviour Approach, Religiosity, commitment and performance, each of which can be specifically reduced into variables as well as the relationship between the grand theory with middle range theory, the respondents in this study were all civil servants in the Jambi Provincial Government. The total sample of respondents was 387 people. To find out whether the model created based on observational data matches the theoretical model or not, a model match index is needed. The results of this research found that leadership behaviour through religiosity values and organizational commitment has an influence on organizational performance in the Jambi provincial government.

KEYWORDS: leadership behavior, religiosity values, organizational commitment, organizational performance, government, public sector.

I. INTRODUCTION

Public sector organizations are organizations that carry out their operational activities using funds originating from the community by orienting their activities towards public services to the community, and are not profit-oriented. One form of public sector organization is government from the central, provincial, district/city government levels, down to village officials. In running this public sector organization, instruments have been formed that must be equipped with duties and obligations, including from the leadership level to the employee level. They will all work together to run the organization to be able to provide the best service to the community and improve the overall performance of the organization.

The performance of providing good service to the community by running a government based on transparent and accountable financial management and being able to provide infrastructure for the community that can be used for daily activities and can improve the regional economy on the basis of the community economy. The success of an organization is influenced by the performance (job performance) of its employees. Every agency or company will make efforts to ensure that its employees provide their best performance in order to contribute to achieving the organizational goals that have been set.

Performance measurement in local government can be done by measuring the performance of the financial and non-financial sectors. The indicators used to measure performance are grouped into input, process, output, outcome, benefit and impact indicators. Local government is a non-profit organization that is included in the pure non-profit organization group. Regional governments are different from business companies, because they have responsibility for managing and controlling regional business and social affairs.

Organizational performance is heavily influenced by factors originating from personal factors, leadership factors, team factors, system factors and contextual factors (Aryee et al., 2007; Ghafoor et al., 2011; Hosseini et al., 2020; Huang et al., 2006; Kawiana, 2019; Lam & O'Higgins, 2012; Schaubroeck et al., 2007; Tyssen et al., 2014; Walumbwa et al., 2010). Several experts also see that organizational performance is influenced by environmental factors, both internal and external (I. Ahmad & Umrani, 2019; Ausat et al., 2022; Hussein et al., 2022; Kalay et al., 2020; Kasemsap, 2013; Metwally et al., 2018; Park et al., 2022).

To be able to achieve this, many factors can support the creation of good regional government performance. Among them are leadership behavior, religious values (Spirituality - Work Ethic) and organizational commitment. If these factors are well embedded, it is hoped that they can increase the desire to work better and produce the right output and outcomes that support the organization's vision and mission.

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II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Leadership behavior is related to the ability to influence people to understand and agree with what needs to be done effectively as well as processes to facilitate individuals and collectives to achieve common goals (G. Yukl, 1989; G. A. Yukl & Becker, 2006). The four components measuring leadership behavior are divided into four dimensions, the first is task-oriented behavior, the second is relationship-oriented behavior, the third is change-oriented behavior and the fourth is external-oriented leadership behavior. Each meta category has a different primary goal, but all goals involve performance determinants. For task-oriented behavior, the primary goal is to complete work in an efficient and reliable manner. For relationship-oriented behavior, the primary goal is to improve the quality of human resources and relationships, which is sometimes called "human capital." For change-oriented behavior, the main goal is to increase innovation, collective learning, and adaptation to the external environment. For external leadership behavior, the primary goals are to obtain necessary information and resources, and to promote and defend the interests of the team or organization.

Organizational commitment (Afshari & Gibson, 2016; N. Ahmad & Oranye, 2010; Edward & Purba, 2020; Kim et al., 2016; McNeese-Smith, 1996; Tan & Lim, 2012; Taufiqurrahman et al., 2021) often defined as (1) a strong desire to remain a member of a particular organization; (2) the desire to strive hard according to the wishes of the organization; and (3) certain beliefs, and acceptance of the organization's values and goals. With indicators of organizational commitment, Meyer and Allen (1991) namely: 1). Affective Commitment is an employee's emotional attachment, identification and involvement in the organization. 2). Continuity Commitment is a commitment based on losses associated with the employee's departure from the organization, this may be due to loss of seniority for promotions or benefits. 3). Normative commitment is a feeling of obligation to remain in the organization because that is the way it has to be; This action is the right thing to do.

Religiosity values commonly used in research, along with several references that support the use of these indicators: Each of these indicators has been studied in the context of research and studies relevant to the field of religion and religious psychology. However, it is important to note that there are variations in the indicators used in these studies. In designing research, researchers must consider research objectives, cultural context, and valid and reliable measurements to best describe religiosity values. Therefore, the researcher created 2 measurement variables which were adjusted to the conditions and circumstances in the research to measure the values of religiosity, namely: Spirituality (Albuquerque et al., 2014; Dubey et al., 2020; Jankowski et al., 2019; Keefe et al., 2001; Rasic et al., 2011; Sani & Ekowati, 2020). Spiritual leadership and army transformation: Theory, measurement, and establishing a baseline. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 22(5), 847-860., and Work Ethic based on Humanistic Work Ethic Theory, Sociological Work Ethic Theory and Classical Work Ethic Theory.

For the Spiritual Dimension of Leadership, as proposed by (Fry et al., 2017), includes four main elements related to leadership that focus on the spiritual dimension. The following are the four dimensions of Spiritual Leadership according to (Fry & Cohen, 2009): 1). Vision: Spiritual leadership leads to the development of an inspirational and transformative vision that transcends personal interests and connects them to higher spiritual values and goals. The vision includes shared goals and provides clear direction to team members. 2). Hope/faith: Spiritual leadership involves cultivating hope and belief in individuals and teams. This involves the belief that challenges can be overcome, necessary resources will be available, and success can be achieved through spiritual support. 3). Altruistic love: This dimension involves genuine care, empathy, and concern for the needs and well-being of team members. Spiritual leadership is based on the values of deep compassion and prioritizing the common good above personal interests. 4). Wisdom: Spiritual leadership involves a deep understanding of spiritual values and wisdom in decision making. Spiritual leaders are able to see holistically, integrate different perspectives, and make decisions that are in accordance with higher spiritual values.

These dimensions reflect a leadership approach that focuses on spiritual and transformative components. They emphasize the importance of inspirational vision, hope/belief, altruistic compassion, and wisdom in influencing others and achieving higher performance in organizational contexts. The dimensions of work ethic are based on Humanistic Work Ethic Theory, Sociological Work Ethic Theory and Classical Work Ethic Theory. Humanistic Work Ethic Theory: A. Self-development dimension: The humanistic work ethic emphasizes the importance of personal development, self-fulfillment, and individual growth through work. This includes intrinsic motivation, self-actualization needs, and personal achievement. B. Dimensions of job satisfaction: The humanistic work ethic highlights job satisfaction as the result of satisfactory personal accomplishment and involvement in work. It involves intrinsic and extrinsic satisfaction related to work. C. Sociological Work Ethic Theory: a. Dimensions of work discipline: The sociological work ethic emphasizes the importance of discipline, responsibility and order in carrying out work duties. This includes a strong work ethic, compliance with rules, and responsibility in carrying out job duties. b. Dimensions of hard work: The sociological work ethic highlights the values of hard work, perseverance and high effort in achieving good results. It involves a spirit of hard work, perseverance, and dedication to achieving work goals. c. Classical Work Ethic Theory: Dimensions of responsibility: The classical work ethic emphasizes the importance of responsibility, discipline, and commitment to work tasks. It involves compliance with rules and regulations, personal responsibility for work, and dedication to achieving good results. Justice dimension: The classic work ethic highlights the values of justice, integrity and honesty in carrying out work duties. It involves moral integrity, honesty, and fair treatment of others in the work environment.

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(Zu et al., 2010) is a result achieved by workers in a particular job that applies to a job with (Afshari & Gibson, 2016) organizational performance indicators/dimensions, namely : a. Individual Factors includes a person's skills, family background, work experience, social level and demographics. b. Psychological factors consist of: Perception, role, attitude, personality, commitment, motivation, culture and job satisfaction. c. Organizational Factors, namely: Organizational Structure, job design.

Figure. 1 Research Model

III. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The outer model concerns testing the validity and reliability of research instruments consisting of:

1) Convergent validity (Convergent Validity)

Based on the results of statistical processing using the WarpPLS7.00 application, it was found that not all indicators met the requirements for a loading score above 0.4 and p-value < 0.05 as seen in Table 5.10 below:

Table 5.1 Combined Loading and Cross-Loading Output

Performance	Y1	Y2	Y3	Y4	Y5	Y6	Y7	Y8	Y9	Y10	Y11	Y12	Y13	Y14	Y15
	0.883	0.652	0.887	0.626	0.548	0.804	0.841	0.826	0.752	0.829	0.912	0.907	0.905	0.919	0.856
S.E	0.045	0.046	0.045	0.047	0.047	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.046	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045
Type (a)	Refl ect														
P value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Behavior	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	X8	X9	X10	X11	X12	X13	X14	X15
	0.91	0.861	0.702	0.868	0.796	0.832	0.839	0.891	0.817	0.823	0.909	0.947	0.893	0.887	0.815
S.E	0.045	0.045	0.046	0.045	0.046	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045
Type (a)	Refl ect														
P value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

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	M1	M2	M3	M4	M5	M6	M7	M8	M9	M10	M11	M12	M13	M14	M15	M16
Religious	0.878	0.896	0.922	0.925	0.939	0.91	0.886	0.838	0.935	0.944	0.812	0.934	0.921	0.919	0.831	0.935
	0.054	0.339	-0.038	0.087	0.131	0.192	-0.046	0.119	-0.109	0.134	-0.306	-0.237	-0.088	-0.01	-0.037	-0.202
S.E	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045	0.045
Type (a)	Reflect															
P value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Commitment	Z1	Z2	Z3	Z4	Z5	Z6
	0.773	0.868	0.802	0.664	0.774	0.662
S.E	0.046	0.045	0.046	0.046	0.046	0.046
Type (a)	Reflect	Reflect	Reflect	Reflect	Reflect	Reflect
P value	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001	<0.001

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Notes: Loadings are unrotated and cross-loadings are oblique-rotated. SEs and P values are for loadings. P values < 0.05 are desirable for reflective indicators.

In Table 5.10, it can be seen that the reflective indicator scores with latent variable scores are above 0.4. Loading scores between 0.4-0.7 were maintained. So from the score obtained from this calculation, the score 0.4 is still used in the model. The required P-value is < 0.05, so that from the P-value calculations in Table 5.12, where the P-value for all indicators is < 0.001, this model can meet the requirements, namely < 0.001 < 0.05. From the indicator scores on the latent variable scores and the P-value obtained, this model can meet *convergent validity*.

2) Discriminant validity (Discriminant validity)

Table 5.2 Output Average variance extracted

Average variances extracted			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.668	0.578	0.814	0.729
Composite reliability coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.967	0.891	0.986	0.976

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Based on Table 5.13, it can be seen that all statements of Average variance extracted and *composite reliability values* have met the discriminant validity requirements. A group of indicators that measure a variable has good composite reliability if it has *Composite reliability* > 0.7

Table 5.3 Latent Variable Coefficients

R-squared coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.808	0.523		
Cronbach's alpha coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.963	0.852	0.985	0.973
Full collinearity of VIFs			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
5.705	2.644	10.035	6.083
Q-squared coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.803	0.523		

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

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output results in Table 5.14, the *R-square* value for the performance variable is 0.808, the political will variable is 0.523. It is known that *composite reliability* has a value of > 0.70 so it can be stated that all variables in this study have met the reliability requirements. The value of the *Full collinearity test* must be < 3.3 so that the model is free from vertical collinearity problems and *common method* bias. It is known that the estimation results show values of 0.803, 0.523 and greater than zero, so that all variables in this study are valid. The variables in the study had *Cronbach's alpha values* greater than 0.6, namely 0.963, 0.852, 0.985 and 0.973.

B. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

1) Coefficient of Determination (R-Squared)

Table 5.4 Output Adjusted R-squared coefficients

Adjusted R-squared coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.807	0.522		

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Based on the data in Table 5.16, it can be seen that the Adjusted R-squared value of the Performance variable is 0.807, based on the criteria by Ferguson (2009), this model includes the criteria for a moderate model. The meaning is that the Performance variable can be explained by the Commitment, Religious, Behavior variables amounting to 80.7%, while the remaining 19.3% is explained by other variables not discussed in this research or other factors outside the model.

The Adjusted R-squared value of the Commitment variable is 0.522, based on the criteria by Ferguson (2009), so this model includes the criteria for a moderate model. The meaning is that the Commitment variable can be explained by the Leadership Behavior variable of 52.2%, while the remaining 47.8% is explained by other variables not discussed in this research or other factors outside the model.

2) Model fit and Quality Indices

Based on Table 5.17, it is known that *the fit and quality indices model* for all criteria meets the requirements so that the research model can be used for analysis.

Table 5.5 Model Fit and Quality Indices

No	Model Fit and Quality Indices	Fit Criteria
1	Average path coefficient (APC)=0.414, $P < 0.001$	$P < 0.05$
2	Average R-squared (ARS)=0.666, $P < 0.001$	$P < 0.05$
3	Average adjusted R-squared (AARS)=0.664, $P < 0.001$	$P < 0.05$
4	Average block VIF (AVIF)=4.307, acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3	Acceptable if < 5 . Ideally < 3.3
5	Average full collinearity VIF (AFVIF)=4.655, acceptable if ≤ 5 , ideally ≤ 3.3	Acceptable if < 5 . Ideally < 3.3
6	Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)=0.451, small ≥ 0.1 , medium ≥ 0.25 , large ≥ 0.36 Tenenhaus GoF (GoF)=0.710, small ≥ 0.1 , medium ≥ 0.25 , large ≥ 0.36	Small ≥ 0.1 Medium ≥ 0.25 , Large. = 0.36
7	Simpson's paradox ratio (SPR)=1,000, acceptable if ≥ 0.7 , ideal = 1	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7 , ideally = 1
8	R-squared contribution ratio (RSCR)=1,000, acceptable if ≥ 0.9 , ideally = 1	Acceptable if ≥ 0.9 , ideally = 1
9	Statistical suppression ratio (SSR)=1,000, acceptable if ≥ 0.7	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7 ,
10	Nonlinear bivariate causality direction ratio (NLBCDR)=1,000, acceptable if ≥ 0.7	Acceptable if ≥ 0.7 ,

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

In Table 5.17 it can be seen that all standard model fit and quality index values in this model have been met as required. This shows that the model in this study has good Goodness of Fit, and there are no multicollinearity problems between indicators and between exogenous variables.

3) Predictive Relevance (Q-squared)

Q-squared or what is usually also called Stoner-Geiser coefficients is a non-parametric measure used to assess the predictive validity or relevance of a set of predictor latent variables on a criterion variable. The criterion for a good model is that the Q-squared value must be greater than zero. The following are the estimation results for Q-squared in this model where the results can be seen in the Output Q-squared coefficients.

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Table 5.6 Output Q-squared coefficients

Q-squared coefficients			
Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
0.803	0.523		

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Based on the estimation results in Table 5.18, it can be seen that the Q-squared value is greater than zero, namely Performance is 0.803 and Commitment is 0.523. So, it can be interpreted that this research model has good predictive validity

4) Effect Size (F-squared effect size)

The effect size is calculated as the absolute value of the individual contribution of each predictor latent variable to the R-squared value of the criterion variable. Effect size is grouped into three criteria, namely weak (0.02), medium (0.15), and large (0.35). The following are the results of the effect size contained in the output effect size for path coefficients

Table 5.7 Output Effect sizes for path coefficients

Effect size for path coefficients				
	Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
Performance		0.397	0.131	0.28
Commitment				0.523

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

the effect size results in Table 5.19, it can be seen that the big influence is: the influence of Commitment on performance, namely 0.397 and Behavior on Commitment, namely 0.523. Meanwhile, those included in the medium category are Religiousness towards Performance, namely 0.131 and behavior towards Performance 0.28. In this study, no one was included in the weak category, because no value was less than 0.02

C. Hypothesis testing

To find out whether there is a significant (significant) relationship or influence between exogenous variables directly and endogenous variables, it can be seen in table 5.20 Direct Effect path coefficient & P Value and is as follows:

Table 5.8 Direct Effect Path Coefficients & P Values

Path coefficients					P values				
	Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior		Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
Performance		0.455	-0.154	0.654	Performance		<0.001	0.001	<0.001
Commitment				0.723	Commitment				<0.001

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

To find out whether there is a significant (significant) relationship or influence between exogenous variables indirectly and endogenous variables, it can be seen in table 5.21 *Indirect and total effect* as follows:

Table 5.9 Indirect and total effects

Indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					Effect sizes of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments				
	Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior		Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
Performance				0.329	Performance				0.283
P values of indirect effects for paths with 2 segments					P values of Sums of indirect effects				
	Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior		Performance	Commitment	Religious	Behavior
Performance				<0.001	Performance				<0.001

Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Figure 5.1 Results of Direct and Indirect Influence Analysis
Source: WarpPLS 7.0 Output Results

Performance is a multidimensional construct that includes many factors that influence it. Performance is *an outcome* resulting from a function of the managerial role of echelon 2 and 3 officials in the organization, and Executives for Echelon 4. This organizational performance variable is measured in three dimensions, namely the first is Individual Factors (skills, family background, work experience, social level and a person's demographics) the second is Psychological Factors (Perceptions, roles, attitudes, personality, commitment, motivation, culture and job satisfaction), and the third is Organizational Factors (Organizational Structure, job design). And made into 15 (fifteen) statements calculated based on the answers to the statements in the questionnaire. where all Organizational performance variable statements all meet the validity criteria.

Organizational performance is the real behavior displayed by each person as work performance produced by employees in accordance with their role in the company. The definition of performance is appearance, the work of personnel both in quality and quantity, the performance of individuals and work groups of personnel, the appearance of work results is not limited to personnel who hold functional or structural positions but also to all levels of personnel within the organization.

The leadership behavior variable in this research is the perception of Echelon II, III and Echelon IV state civil servants regarding organizational performance. Leadership behavior generally means certain actions in which a leader is involved in the process of directing and coordinating the work of his group members. This may involve actions such as structuring work relationships, praising or criticizing group members, and showing consideration for their well-being and feelings. Leadership behavior is a leadership style in implementing leadership functions, which has a huge influence and is very decisive in making the organization effective in achieving its goals. The behavioral theory approach through leadership style in the realization of leadership functions is a leadership strategy that has two orientations consisting of task orientation and subordinate orientation.

A person's leadership behavior is unique and cannot be inherited automatically. Each leader has certain characteristics that arise in different situations. Leadership behavior is behavior and strategy, as a result of a combination of philosophy, skills, traits and attitudes that a leader often applies when trying to influence the performance of his subordinates.

In carrying out daily tasks, leaders must be based on a leadership orientation that is applied through the behavior they implement. Leader behavior is the behavior or methods chosen and used by leaders to influence the thoughts, feelings, attitudes and behavior of organizational members or subordinates. The relationship between leaders and subordinates can be measured through workers' assessments of the leadership style of leaders in directing and coaching their subordinates to carry out work. This leadership behavior variable is measured through 4 (four) dimensions and 15 (fifteen) statements which are calculated based on the answers to the statements in the questionnaire. From the statistical results, it was found that all research questionnaires for Leadership Behavior Variables all met the validity criteria.

Organizational Commitment is the perception of echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV state civil servants regarding the Organizational Performance of the Jambi Provincial Government. Organizational commitment refers to an individual's level of loyalty, identification, and involvement with the organization where they work. It reflects an individual's level of attachment to the goals, values, mission and sustainability of the organization. The concept of organizational commitment is important because it has significant implications for individual performance, employee retention, job satisfaction, and overall organizational productivity.

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In addition to this type of commitment, there is also an integrative approach that combines the components of this type of commitment. Regardless of the type of commitment an individual has, the higher the level of organizational commitment, the greater the likelihood that the individual will remain in the organization, contribute positively, and achieve desired results. Dimensions of organizational commitment refer to aspects that describe the level of individual commitment to the organization in which they work. There are several dimensions of organizational commitment that are commonly used in management research and practice.

The Organizational Commitment variable in this study was measured using 3 (three) dimensions and 6 (six) statements contained in the statement in the questionnaire. Responses to this statement can describe the condition of perceptions of Organizational Commitment. The Organizational Commitment variables in this study all meet the validity criteria.

The Religiosity variable referred to in this research is the Perception of Jambi Provincial Government civil servants echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV with the explanation that Religiosity is a process of seeking a path to truth that is related to something sacred.

Religiosity comes from the Latin word for religion "religion", with the root word religere meaning "to bind". Religion, or religion in general, has rules and obligations that must be followed and fulfilled by its adherents, and all of this functions to bind a person or group of people in relation to God, fellow humans, and the natural environment. Religiosity is an attitude towards human diversity or activities related to religion. Religiosity according to Islamic teachings can be identified through several important aspects, namely through the components of belief in religious teachings (aqidah), obedience to religious teachings (shariah or worship), aspects of respect for religious teachings (ihsan) and aspects of knowledge about religion. religious teachings (knowledge) and aspects of implementing religious teachings in social life (Muamalah under the guidance of Akhlaq al-karimah). Religiosity has five dimensions, namely the dimension of belief, the dimension of religious worship or practice, the dimension of experience, the dimension of intellectual and religious knowledge, the dimension of application.

The public service motivation variable in this study was measured by 2 variables, namely spiritualism and work ethic with 7 (seven) dimensions and 16 statements contained in the statements in the questionnaire. Responses to this statement can describe the condition of religiosity. The religiosity variables in this study all meet the validity criteria.

resulting *Adjusted R-squared* value, it can be seen that the *Adjusted R-squared value* of the Organizational Performance variable is 0.807, based on the criteria by Ferguson (2009), so this model includes the criteria for a moderate model. The meaning is that the Organizational Performance variable can be explained by the Leadership Behavior, Commitment and Religiosity variables amounting to 80.7%, while the remaining 19.3% is explained by other variables not discussed in this research or other factors outside the model.

Adjusted R-squared value of the Commitment variable is 0.522, based on the criteria by Ferguson (2009), so this model includes the criteria for a moderate model. The meaning is that the Commitment variable can be explained by the leadership behavior variable of 52.2%, while the remaining 47.8% is explained by other variables not discussed in this research or other factors outside the model.

D. Novelty of Research

Novelty model in this research to refine concepts and research methods. The concept is supported by expert opinion and several previous studies which strengthen the use of research methods, namely data analysis which uses the SEM-PLS tool assisted by WarpPLS software Version 7.0 (latest version) which is in accordance with the research model to answer the hypothesis. Based on the results of testing the determining factors for the performance of echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV State Civil Apparatus Organizations in the Jambi provincial government, namely: (1) Leadership behavior influences performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly, (2), Leadership behavior influences organizational commitment in government Jambi province positively and significantly, (3), Religiosity values influence organizational performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly, (4), organizational commitment Influence organizational performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly, (5), Behavior leadership Weakens the influence of organizational performance, moderated by religiosity values in the Jambi provincial government significantly, (6), Leadership behavior influences organizational performance, mediated by organizational commitment in the Jambi provincial government, positively and significantly.

The State Civil Apparatus echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV of the Jambi provincial government in carrying out their main duties and functions as managers and implementers cannot be separated from factors that can support the achievement and improvement of their managerial performance, including leadership behavior, commitment and religious values. which is built by Spirituality and Work Ethic. Statistically, based on *the effect size results*, it can be seen that there is a weak influence on the influence of leadership behavior on the performance of echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV state civil servants of the Jambi provincial government which is moderated by religious values. Meanwhile, those included in the medium category are the influence of commitment on organizational performance and the influence of leadership behavior on organizational performance. Included in the large category is the influence of leadership behavior on organizational commitment.

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If you look at the comparison based on statistical results, which is stronger, the role of mediation and the role of moderation in improving organizational performance? The answer is the mediating role of the Commitment variable. The commitment variable is able to be a stronger mediating variable than the Moderating Role of the Religiosity variable, although both are equally capable of mediating and moderating the influence of leadership behavior on organizational performance, but statistically the total effect value is the largest through the Commitment Variable.

Apart from that, the novelty of the research is summarized again: (1) As far as the author is concerned, the research subject has never been researched; (2) Overall, the research model based on research objects/variables has never been studied (3) To answer the hypothesis in the research model using SEM-PLS with the help of the WarpPLS V.70 application, which is the latest version that supports the research model; (5) There is a role of moderation and mediation in a research model which is still little done by previous researchers .

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusion

The conclusions of this research are: *Model fit* and *quality indices* in this model have been met;

1. Leadership behavior influences performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly. Overall, effective leadership behavior can create a positive work climate, motivate employees, increase coordination and collaboration, and direct efforts towards organizational goals. All of these factors contribute to better organizational performance and long-term success. Effective leadership behavior to maximize organizational performance includes a number of aspects that contribute to achieving optimal results.
2. Leadership behavior influences organizational commitment in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly, with the level of individual commitment to the organization. Leaders who are able to inspire, motivate, and guide their followers tend to increase the level of individual commitment to the organization.
3. Religiosity values influence organizational performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly, to improve performance what must be done is Morality and Ethics, then Commitment and dedication, Leadership Based on Values and Employee Welfare and finally Collaboration and Harmony
4. Organizational commitment influences organizational performance in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly. When individuals feel attached and committed to the organization, they tend to have higher motivation, better attendance levels, and higher performance. Organizational commitment can also influence employee engagement, employee retention, and job satisfaction, which in turn can contribute to overall organizational performance.
5. Leadership behavior Weakens the influence of organizational performance moderated by religiosity values in the Jambi provincial government significantly, individuals with high levels of religiosity may show different responses to leadership behavior, which can then influence their performance in the organizational context.
6. Leadership behavior influences organizational performance mediated by organizational commitment in the Jambi provincial government positively and significantly. Good leadership behavior, namely being able to provide rewards and recognition, can influence the level of individual commitment to the organization. High organizational commitment, especially affective and normative commitment, can have a positive impact on individual performance and overall organizational performance

V. SUGGESTION

Based on the research results, the author provides suggestions that can be useful for echelon II, echelon III and echelon IV State Civil Apparatus of the Jambi provincial government as well as Regional Heads in improving organizational performance relating to the implementation of roles and functions. The suggestions from the author are as follows:

1) Academic Advice

- a. The research results are used to develop human resource management studies, especially the managerial performance of officials in carrying out their roles and functions as managers.
- b. The research results can be used as reference material in the development of management science, especially in the implementation function, namely in the aspects of leadership behavior, commitment and religious values formed by spirituality and work ethic. In this research, organizational performance is explained by the factors of leadership behavior, commitment, and religious values which are formed by spirituality and work ethic . There are still other factors that can influence managerial performance so it is recommended that further research include or replace them with other variables to obtain more varied research results.

2) Pragmatic Advice

- a. Regional heads are advised to have leadership behavior to collaborate because their leadership abilities in collaboration are considered not optimal by officials.

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- b. Regional heads are advised to re-evaluate the placement of officials because conditions are considered that the placement of employees is not in accordance with their area of expertise, there are still many officials who believe that they are placed in positions that are not in accordance with their area of expertise resulting in a lack of optimal commitment to the organization.
- c. Regional heads are advised to be able to implement a good reporting management information system because conditions are considered to be that the reporting relationship between superiors and subordinates is relatively not running optimally and there are obstacles.
- d. Regional heads are advised to instill an understanding of religious values in the activities of all employees.
- e. The State Civil Apparatus of the Jambi provincial government is advised to be more stringent in pursuing various methods to achieve organizational goals because conditions indicate weaknesses in achieving organizational goals .
- f. The State Civil Apparatus of the Jambi provincial government is advised to practice serving without compensation because conditions show that officials' awareness of serving without compensation is relatively low.

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